

EVALUATION OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The article describes the criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the management activities of teaching staff in higher education institutions, indicators of the implementation of these criteria, and presents proposals for assessing effectiveness in higher education institutions.

Keywords: education, higher education, management, administration, professors, students, management characteristics, management effectiveness, evaluation criteria.

Introduction. Today, one of the main directions of development of the educational sector is aimed at increasing the efficiency of educational services and entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, our scientists attach special importance to the study of this area. Based on this, our research was also focused on improving ways to increase the efficiency of educational services and entrepreneurial activities in higher education institutions.

Since our country gained independence, we have been paying great attention to education. In particular, our first President, I.A. Karimov, emphasized: “We must not forget that the foundation of our future is laid in educational institutions, in other words, the future of our people depends on how our children are educated and raised today¹”. Today, the education sector is the constant focus of our President. The current era demands rapid innovation in every field. The only way to achieve this is to organize quality education.

In the current digital economy, innovation is developing rapidly in every sector. Also, innovation is being given great importance in the education system, including the higher education system. The role of innovation in improving the quality and efficiency of educational services is incomparable.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Higher Issues related to improving the management of the education system were discussed by our scientists S.S.G'ulomov, A.T.Shermuhammedovlar², M.A.Ikromov³, M.Q.Pardaev⁴, M.E.Po'latov, Q.X.Abdurakhmonov, Sh.R.Kholmo'minov, N.Q.Zokirova⁵ are engaged in this. These authors have published a number of literature and scientific articles. They mainly cover issues such as improving the education system, digital economy, implementing digital education, and personnel management.

Research methodology. The article used methods such as spatial and temporal, logical, and comparative analysis of teaching staff management in the higher education system.

Analysis and results. In recent years, the main attention of authors studying the problems of interaction between the education system and the labor market has been paid to the quantitative and qualitative compliance of graduates of higher education institutions with the needs of regional labor markets⁶. Thus, according to modern views on the effectiveness of higher education, it has several directions in which it manifests itself (Figure 1).

Figure 4.6. Higher education institutions and supreme education efficiency manifestation to be directions

From the state point of view, the economic efficiency of higher education, first of all, represents a higher efficiency of budgetary investments in the field of education than investments directed to other sectors of the economy, provided that losses are reduced as a result of the redistribution of budget funds in favor of education. The social efficiency of higher education at the state level is determined by the social stabilization of society and is manifested in the growth of the standard of living of the population. Economic efficiency at the level of the national economy is determined by changes in the quality of labor and scientific potential, an increase in labor productivity and, ultimately, GDP growth. In the educational services market, the management of a higher educational institution and its effectiveness are reflected in the competitiveness of its activities and its overall position in the market.

In this case, it is more appropriate to talk about economic efficiency, although the commercial understanding of this term is not complete, since for higher educational institutions, profit is not a separate goal. In this case, the indicators that determine economic efficiency are general (budgetary and extrabudgetary): the volume of income, the level of expenses, as well as the composition of expenses of higher educational institutions, which determine competitive stability and real opportunities.

From the point of view of the regional labor market, including in the case of positive dynamics of employment and unemployment rates among young people, one can speak of the social effectiveness of higher education, while economic effectiveness is determined, in general, by the level of economic efficiency and GRP growth at the regional economy level⁷.

The economic efficiency of higher education for the employer is, first of all, the difference between the highest income received by the industry as a result of hiring the appropriate specialist and the costs of his training and salary. As for the individual, as

mentioned above, the efficiency of higher professional education can be discussed in two directions: the economic efficiency of investing in education, taking into account the opportunity costs of foregone education, and social efficiency in the form of increasing the professional level and, as a result, the position in society⁸.

Thus, the efficiency of higher education is a multifaceted category that includes economic and social components. However, it is worth noting that in this case we are talking, first of all, about the efficiency of higher professional education within the framework of regional and national socio-economic systems or about the efficiency of a particular educational service for a particular consumer-student/graduate of higher education. Only some of the considered aspects of the efficiency of higher education can be directly related to the success of a particular higher educational institution: the competitiveness of higher educational institutions in the educational services market as a result of effective management, as well as as a result of efficiency for the employer, but only under the condition of his financial participation in training or participation in the development of a specialist, since otherwise the educational service is not obligatory for a particular higher educational institution. It is also important that, taking into account the interests of all participants in the processes of training, employment and further professional activity of specialists with higher education in higher educational institutions, a number of contradictions arise regarding the content and duration of the intended benefits. In this regard, the understanding of the category of the term "activity efficiency" in relation to a higher educational institution arises taking into account modern economic and social conditions, which determine the need for it to function as an effective subject of the national economy in a broad sense⁹.

The generalization and revision of the above approaches allowed the author to formulate the following definition of the term "effectiveness of the activities of a higher educational institution": the effectiveness of the activities of a higher educational institution is a socio-economic category that comprehensively reflects the general public and individual results of the use of internal and external resources in the process of satisfying a system of multi-level needs for specialists with higher professional education by a higher educational institution.

In our opinion, it is also necessary to distinguish between such terms as "efficiency of higher education institutions", "effectiveness of higher education institutions", "competitiveness of higher education institutions" and "quality of education or quality of educational services", since, despite the existing differences, these terms are often used as synonyms. The efficiency of higher education institutions allows us to assess the qualitative and quantitative results of various areas of activity of higher education institutions without resource costs. Moreover, in this case, costs are not considered an object of assessment at all, since the main financial result is the amount of income received by the educational institution, labor resources, information resources and material resources are assessed by their quality. The competitiveness of higher education institutions, as noted above, is an indicator of the efficiency of management of a higher education institution, that is, the result of the activities of higher education institutions, at the same time we can talk about the category of "quality of educational services", which characterizes the efficiency of educational activities of higher education institutions.

Also, according to the author, the efficiency of higher education institutions of vocational education should be considered from several perspectives. For example: from the point of view of the state as a customer and guarantor of meeting the needs of society (macroefficiency); from the point of view of the individual as a consumer of educational services (individual investment efficiency); from the point of view of the regional labor market and a specific employer - a consumer of the products of higher education institutions

(market efficiency); from the point of view of the activities of higher education institutions as an economic entity.

All the other efficiency indicators of higher education considered above cannot be determined in relation to a specific educational institution, since they appear as a general result of the activities of the entire higher education system, or have an external character that arises in the process of training higher education institutions and the subsequent employment of a specialist with higher education. A generalized description of efficiency, in our opinion, can be called the integral efficiency of the activities of higher education institutions, since the aspects proposed for consideration are to a certain extent interconnected and characterized by interaction¹⁰.

Our research also deeply analyzed modern national and foreign experiences in providing temporary employment to university students. We believe that this issue deserves special attention, since its proper organization has a positive impact on all areas of higher education institutions' activities.

Based on this analysis, the following conclusions were drawn: In Uzbek practice, temporary work is considered by students as the main source of income or as an opportunity to combine leisure with earning a certain amount of income in the summer; in the absence of a systematic policy in the field of temporary employment of students, the priorities for combining work and study with full-time students are not formed in favor of mastering theoretical knowledge, which negatively affects the work of students who work a lot.

We also propose conceptual approaches to improving the activities of higher education institutions as a source of satisfying a multi-level system of needs for highly educated specialists: national, regional, subject. In the current conditions, the effective functioning of higher education institutions, in our opinion, should be organized on the basis of the basic principles of strategic management, but taking into account the specific socio-economic role of the educational institution as a non-profit organization¹¹. In our opinion, the following aspects should be accepted as the main methodological principles for implementing the scientific concept of the effective functioning of higher education institutions: the economic and social complexity of higher education institutions as an object of management determines the complexity of the management system, but not exceeding the objectively necessary level; the priorities of managing higher education institutions should be formed equally in the zone of ensuring target indicators of social efficiency and in the zone of economic efficiency; the interests of users of educational services of higher educational institutions are of primary importance, the interests of state entities are of secondary importance, therefore, the strategic management of higher educational institutions should not be aggressive towards the external environment; strategies for the complex socio-economic development of regions, strategies for the development of the labor market, national strategies are considered as environmental factors of the strategy for the development of higher educational institutions, which determines the need to coordinate it with high-level goals¹²; effective organization of the activities of higher educational institutions should be aimed at solving the following tasks: increasing the effectiveness of the interaction between the educational services market and the national and regional labor market and, as a result, the national economy; increasing the economic independence of higher educational institutions, the stability and flexibility of their management structure; increasing the effectiveness of the interaction between higher educational institutions and private business entities, creating a favorable situation in the buyer behavior of the applicant in the labor market and the economy as a whole. The work

outlines the main directions for improving the efficiency of higher education institutions in accordance with the set tasks.

Against the background of the processes taking place in the economy and society today, including the process of servitization in society and the economy, higher educational institutions must adequately respond to all socio-economic changes. On the one hand, the source of formation and replenishment of the labor potential of the economy, and on the other hand, in order to increase the integral efficiency of educational institutions, which are one of the largest segments of the service sector, the vocational education system should expand the service component of the implemented educational programs as an independent qualification or as a full-fledged structural module within the curriculum. The main idea of these changes is to provide the national economy with service specialists who have specialized industrial education and are able to organize, manage and adjust all service processes that are part of the reproduction cycle¹³. To achieve this goal, the service sector, higher education, must fairly solve a number of tasks.

Conclusions and proposals. Content development: formation of a component of higher specialized education in the service sector, taking into account the need to train specialists for the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of a competent approach to the service component in the production and sale of goods and services; development of a republican system for forecasting and monitoring the need for training specialists in various professions to ensure the functioning of service sectors and, on this basis, the formation of a state order system for multidisciplinary educational institutions implementing service training programs; development of a system for assessing the practical orientation of vocational education programs at all levels in the service sector and assigning a regional rating to vocational education institutions; organization of the implementation of DTS (state education standards) of higher vocational education in the service sector, creation of infrastructure: using advanced world experience, in cooperation with educational institutions and employers, to form a system of basic training centers for service specialties (training hotels, enterprises, dry cleaning industries, car services, beauty salons, ateliers, etc.); to create corporate institutes (faculties) in the service sector; to form service profiles of the innovation belt on the basis of higher educational institutions, including technology transfer centers, management centers, venture capital funds, etc.; to create business incubators for small and medium-sized businesses in the service sector on the basis of educational institutions as an innovative collective program; to develop models and mechanisms for creating a system of certification centers to assess the professional qualifications of graduates of all levels of service industries and vocational training programs¹⁴.

Building human resources: training specialists, teaching staff and trainers for higher professional education levels in the service sector using specially developed programs taking into account the most advanced domestic and foreign experiences; forming a systematic base of personnel training and retraining centers on the basis of existing educational institutions implementing educational programs for the service sector; improving the system of professional retraining and certification of senior service personnel, taking into account the requirements for the introduction and use of quality management standards in the service sector; training entrepreneurial personnel for the development of small and medium-sized businesses in the service sector.

Development of organizational and economic management mechanisms: development of mechanisms for state support in the formation of programs for the development of regional educational institutions implementing personnel training programs for the service sector; development of mechanisms for interaction between educational institutions, regional social and professional organizations and employers' associations aimed at forming requirements

for the qualifications of graduates of vocational education programs at all levels for the service sector.

Information support: organization of thematic exhibitions in various areas of service provision; creation of joint print media and Internet resources; similar events limited to the network characteristics of a particular type of service; development of models of interaction between employers and educational institutions to promote service products and educational programs in the service sector, etc.; development and launch of the Internet portal "Service Education" for general use; organization of a resource center for the development of an educational and innovative information environment in the field of vocational education in the service sector in order to provide open access to new educational resources with access to the above-mentioned Internet portal.

Solving the tasks set, in our opinion, is a priority area for improving the effectiveness of the educational activities of higher educational institutions and service higher educational institutions that train specialists with a service component in their professional activities.

According to the results of the study, mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of higher education institutions were proposed, which include the most promising forms of cooperation between business and higher education institutions of Uzbekistan in terms of integrated efficiency improvement. In our opinion, these are professional academies (for applied and branch higher education institutions), university-based educational and production complexes, including small industries, student research laboratories (industries), educational and scientific-innovative complexes (for leading higher education institutions with an appropriate scientific base), partnerships and the development of this form.

The proposed forms of interaction, in our opinion, will allow us to ensure the following: from the point of view of macro-efficiency of the activities of higher educational institutions: development of fair competition in the educational services market; testing of new organizational structures of organizational and legal forms of alliance with business; development of proposals for further improvement of the regulatory and legal framework for reforming the higher education system; multiplication of best practices; development of multi-channel financing mechanisms; sufficiently accurate long-term forecast of the need for specialists of the appropriate level, including quantitative and qualitative indicators; involvement of employers in the activities of vocational education institutions, ensuring the quality of specialist training by monitoring the results of specialist training within the framework of the corporate system of attestation and certification of graduates' qualifications; testing and widespread implementation of mechanisms for interaction between higher educational institutions and employers; from the point of view of market efficiency of the activities of higher educational institutions: participation of business, including employers, in the educational, scientific and management activities of the educational institution in accordance with advanced international experience from the point of view of the results of labor of the end user of the educational institution and investors; development and improvement of educational standards, curricula and a system of training highly qualified personnel taking into account the needs of the labor market; creation and development of educational-production-technological infrastructure on the basis of higher educational institutions to ensure the innovative activities of companies; involvement of students and teachers in the educational process to conduct research and prepare projects to solve specific business problems; the possibility of providing employees of the sectors with continuing education; from the point of view of economic efficiency: development of the material and technical base of the educational institution and formation of additional opportunities for multi-channel financing; creation of a new model of an integrated educational complex (high-quality management, new infrastructure, technologies and places for training students and teachers); improvement of the quality of educational services by involving employers in the development of the content of educational programs and

providing the necessary base for updating the practical components, including internships; development of new models of educational, scientific, production and institutional integration; increasing the financial security of scientific research of scientists, teachers and students of an educational institution (additional financing of scientific developments and their commercialization with patenting and copyright); increasing competitiveness in the educational services market; satisfaction of the expected results from receiving educational services in the form of the opportunity to get a job in the chosen specialty and a high level of competitiveness in the labor market for the consumer-applicant/student in terms of individual investment efficiency.

As mentioned above, management effectiveness can only be achieved if management is approached correctly, the right decisions are made, and the implementation of these decisions and orders is monitored and evaluated.

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